

Figure 4b: The 8x8 vāstu, KI 54.30-37

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|----------------|---------------|-------------|
| 1 Brahmā | 19 Satya | 37 Roga |
| 2 Marīcaka | 20 Bhṛṣa | 38 Vāyu |
| 3 Vivasvant | 21 Antarikṣa | 39 Nāga |
| 4 Mitra | 22 Agni | 40 Mukhya |
| 5 Pṛthivīdhara | 23 Pūṣan | 41 Bhallāṭa |
| 6 Āpa | 24 Vitatha | 42 Soma |
| 7 Āpavatsa | 25 Gṛhākṣata | 43 Ṛgi |
| 8 Savitṛ | 26 Yama | 44 Aditi |
| 9 Sāvitrī | 27 Gandharva | 45 Diti |
| 10 Indra | 28 Bhṛṅga | |
| 11 Indrajit | 29 Mṛga | |
| 12 Rudra | 30 Piṭṛ | |
| 13 Rudradāsa | 31 Dauvārika | |
| 14 Īśa | 32 Sugrīva | |
| 15 Parjanya | 33 Puṣpadanta | |
| 16 Jaya | 34 Pracetas | |
| 17 Mahendra | 35 Asura | |
| 18 Sūrya | 36 Śoṣa | |

The demons outside the vāstu are not described.

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37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	14	
36		13					6		15	
		12						7		
35		5						16		
34				1		2		17		
33		4						18		
32		3						19		
31	11	10					9	8	20	
30		28	27	26	25	24	23		21	
	29								22	